

TYPES OF TRADING AND THEIR PECULIARITIES**Nosir Sherboyev**

a teacher of National university of
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Language is a complex system of characters with conceptual content. Among the basic functions of the language, it is necessary to cite such as communication (communication), cognitive (thinking), cumulative (accumulation and storage of knowledge), nominative (naming things and objects), emotive-expressive (manifesting emotionality, reacting). It is argued by researchers that language is a cultural phenomenon, a derivative of social interaction.

The founder of theoretical linguistics, baron Wilhelm von Humboldt (Wilhelm von Humboldt), recognizes the integrity of language and the national spirit, the determinant of national thought. In the linguistic concept put forward by Humboldt, language is defined as a self-developing organism.

There are many functions of language, all of which are embodied in the expression of thought. Through the language and through the various tools in it, different goals are achieved. In the street, tevarak-around and, especially in the market, through the language and a number of its functions, various purchase and sale works are carried out. A skilled trader uses the rhetorical tools of language to attract customers to buy trading goods. In this, a skilled merchant can skillfully use his speech and create a kind of rhetoric. The scientific field that we are researching is also related to the speech of trade workers. The language or languages we speak, read and write about have a significant impact on economic, social and Human Development. Language determines cultural identity and thus influences people's decisions, including economic ones. Although various scientific disciplines have long been studying issues of cultural and linguistic diversity, the economy of languages began to take shape only in the second half of the 20th century. In this chapter on the example of economic literature, we studied classical and modern methodological, theoretical and empirical studies, interpreted our review around linguistic diversity and its influence.

In the last century, there has been much debate about the language and its functions. The question of whether language is capable of determining thinking and behavior has long been the subject of scientific debate. In the middle of the twentieth century, American linguists Edward Sepir and Benjamin Varf put

forward the ideas of linguistic relativity in their works: they believed that the structure of a language affects how its speakers perceive the world - so people who speak different languages and dialects insist on forming different ideas about reality. They were challenged by the famous linguist and philosopher Noam Khomsky with his idea of a universal grammar – that is, a unified structure of all languages, which he repeatedly insisted could not predict the various perceptions of the world or behavior as a result. In our opinion, we can further enrich our speech using not only grammatical categories of the language, but also phonetic and lexical categories. We have given feedback on how to use linguistic data for an economic purpose to test the Vorf Sepir hypothesis. We witnessed that in the market there are more people attracted by good-natured, fluent speakers, sales employees whose language is burro, that is, who perfectly occupy all the categories of the language.

At the same time, The Economist Keith Chen drew our minds to the idea that "people tend to save and analyze the impact of the future on other economic decisions of how time is formed in their language." In our markets, too, we hear a lot of calls from the next modern Feli: "your cattle will go with you", "you will still come back again". Through these statements, the sellers are assured that the goods they are selling have a future and will come back again in the future, in our eyes. Native speakers of languages less connected to the Future Tense, such as German or Chinese, where the same verb form can be used in the present and next tense, save more. The reason for this is the impression of the next and present in the minds of speakers as if they meant a single concept between themselves. For native speakers of languages where the Future Tense is formed by a different verb form – such as English or Spanish – the future appears longer, reducing the motivation of their speakers to save money. For example, "Buy it, please! You will not regret!", "I will guarantee that you will definitely dress this cloth for the next five years!", causing the idea to come that the money they spend will not lose its value even in the minds of the buyer in the distant future. The foundations of language economics were laid in a 1965 paper by prominent American economist Jacob Marshak that applied standard economic concepts of costs and benefits to language. Marshak's research immediately attracted the attention of economists after its emergence, but at the first stage their interest was focused primarily on language economics and reforms in the field. The fact that language plays a very important role for the economy can be learned from the views of this scientist. According to him, the more culture the people of trade speak, the greater the number and loyalty of the consumers. The ability to

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communicate with people is a brand that can be bought as we buy tea or coffee, but I am willing to pay more for this product than anything else, wrote the American entrepreneur Dj. D. Rockefeller.

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